

Status of the Hyper-Kamiokande experiment

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Hyper-Kamiokande experiment

Next generation multi-purpose neutrino and nucleon decay experiment
Continuation and upgrade to both Super-Kamiokande and T2K experiments
Scheduled to begin operations in 2028

Improved neutrino beam

Staged upgrade of J-PARC neutrino beam from 0.5 MW → 1.3 MW

Hyper-K expected to collect 2.7×10^{21} POT / year

In 2024 achieved 954 kW in test, running stably with 830 kW

Increased horn current 250 kA → 320 kA

► Increases neutrino flux by ~10%, reduced wrong sign contamination

Upgraded near detectors

Extensive suit of detectors to study flux and interactions of unoscillated neutrinos

Significantly reduce flux and interaction systematic uncertainties at the far detector

- ▶ Target systematics below 4%, long term to <2%

Detector upgrade completed in 2024

- ▶ Improve angular acceptance to 4π and lower energy threshold for protons

Further upgrade to ND280++ in the future

Event number : 345342 | Run number : 16847 | Spill : 28852 | Time : Fri 2024-06-07 18:29:00 JST | Trigger: Beam Spill

See [yesterday's talk](#) on performance of the upgraded detector in T2K by Camilla Forza

See talks by [Ewan Miller](#) and [Daniel Ferlewicz](#) on future upgrades

New intermediate detector

Water-Cherenkov detector movable between 1.5° to 4° off-axis angles

Equipped with multi-PMTs

Facility building and excavation ongoing

See [talk](#) by Ryosuke Akutsu later today

New and larger far detector

Proven water Cherenkov detector technology
600 m under Mt. Niijuga-yama near Kamioka

Increased size

- ▶ 250 kT of water, 8x fiducial volume of Super-K

20,000 upgraded 20" PMTs

- ▶ 2x improved detection efficiency and timing resolution
- ▶ 20% photo-coverage

800 multi-PMTs

- ▶ Improved directional resolution, dark rate, calibration

Improved reconstruction

- ▶ Faster, added novel machine learning tools

Supernova

Atmospheric

Solar

Broad and ambitious physics programme covering many neutrino sources as well as nucleon decays and dark matter

Accelerator

Sensitivity to solar neutrinos

~130 solar neutrino events per day!

Continue precision measurements of solar neutrino oscillation parameters

After 10 years 5σ discovery for day/night asymmetry and $3-5\sigma$ for “upturn”

- ▶ Investigate tension between KamLAND and other solar neutrino results
- ▶ Study potential Beyond Standard Model physics

Detect hep solar neutrinos with $2-3\sigma$

Sensitivity to supernova neutrinos

Large event rate for Milky Way supernovae

- ▶ ~80k for galactic centre ~10 kpc
- ▶ ~3000 for 50 kpc (SN1987 – Kamiokande saw 11 events)
- ▶ ~10 events for supernovae in Andromeda
- ▶ DAQ designed to handle event rate for very near supernovae

Diffuse Supernova Neutrino Background (DSNB)

- ▶ 4.2 σ observation within 10 years and 5.7 σ in 20 years
- ▶ ~18 events/year

arXiv:1109.3262

Sensitivity to nucleon decays

Constrain Grand Unified Theories

Super-K currently holds best constraint on almost all decay modes

Hyper-K will set new world-leading limits beyond an order of magnitude above the current ones

[HK] [arXiv:1805.04163](https://arxiv.org/abs/1805.04163)

[DUNE] [arXiv:2002.03005](https://arxiv.org/abs/2002.03005)

[JUNO] [arXiv:1508.07166](https://arxiv.org/abs/1508.07166)

Hyper-K neutrino oscillations sensitivity

Beam only sensitivity studies submitted to EPJC: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.15019>

5 σ discovery of CP violation in 10 years for ~60% of true δ_{CP} values!

- ▶ Assuming known mass ordering \rightarrow adding atmospheric events will help constrain mass ordering
- ▶ In <3 years for $\delta_{CP} = -\pi/2$, normal hierarchy

Targeting better than 20% precision on all δ_{CP} values in 10 years

Hyper-K preliminary

True normal ordering (known) **HK 10 Years (2.7×10^{22} POT 1:3 $\nu\bar{\nu}$)**

$\sin^2\theta_{13}=0.0218 \pm 0.0007$, $\sin^2\theta_{23}=0.528$, $\Delta m_{32}^2=2.509 \times 10^{-3} \text{eV}^2/c^4$

Hyper-K preliminary

True normal ordering (known), Improved systematics

$\sin^2\theta_{13}=0.0218 \pm 0.0007$, $\sin^2\theta_{23}=0.528$, $\Delta m_{32}^2=2.509 \times 10^{-3} \text{eV}^2/c^4$

Hyper-K neutrino oscillations sensitivity

Beam only sensitivity studies submitted to EPJC: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.15019>

Wrong octant rejection at 5σ in 10 years for most true $\sin^2\theta_{23}$ values

With atmospheric exclude wrong mass ordering with $\sim 4-6\sigma$, depending on true $\sin^2\theta_{23}$

0.4% precision on Δm^2_{23} , 0.4-2% precision on $\sin^2\theta_{23}$

Hyper-K preliminary
 True normal ordering (known), 10 years (2.7×10^{22} POT 1:3 $\nu\bar{\nu}$)
 $\sin^2\theta_{13} = 0.0218 \pm 0.0007$, $\delta_{CP} = -1.601$, $\Delta m^2_{32} = 2.509 \times 10^{-3} \text{eV}^2/c^4$

An aerial, top-down view of a massive circular cavern excavation. The cavern's interior walls are lined with large, rectangular concrete panels. In the center, a large, circular concrete structure is visible, featuring a complex network of white-painted structural beams. To the right of this central structure, a small, elevated platform or walkway is situated, with a few workers and equipment visible on it. The floor of the cavern is uneven and appears to be a mix of dirt and concrete. The lighting is dim, with several bright spots from overhead lights illuminating the scene.

**Cavern excavation
completed 31st July 2025**

Hyper-K cavern from the top

Excavation and construction

The cavern excavation completed 31st July 2025

Video describing the excavation process [here](#)

Tank construction ongoing, PMT installation in 2027

Conclusion

Hyper-Kamiokande is a next generation multi-purpose neutrino and nucleon decay experiment

- ▶ Proven water-Cherenkov technology with significantly improved capabilities
- ▶ Upgraded beamline and near detectors, new intermediate detector
- ▶ Excavation complete, tank construction in progress

Very broad physics program

- ▶ Superb supernova and DSNB detection
- ▶ On route to be the first experiment to discover CP violation in the lepton sector
- ▶ Very large statistics for high-precision studies

Hyper-Kamiokande will be the world leading experiment in δCP , DSNB, and nucleon decays for the next 20 years!

Thank you!

(Some) Hyper-K collaborators inside the almost excavated cavern

Backup

Hyper-K Schedule

The cavern excavation completed 31st July 2025, Currently ongoing tank wall lining
PMT installation starts in 2027, scheduled to begin operations in 2028

Neutrino Oscillations

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e) = 4s_{23}^2 s_{13}^2 c_{13}^2 \sin^2 \Delta_{31} \quad \text{Leading term}$$

$$\mp J_{\text{CP}} \sin \Delta_{32} \sin \Delta_{31} \sin \Delta_{21} \quad \text{CP-odd term}$$

$$\pm 8a(1 - 2s_{13}^2) s_{23}^2 s_{13}^2 c_{13}^2 \frac{\sin \Delta_{31}}{\Delta m_{31}^2} (\sin \Delta_{31} - \Delta_{31} \cos \Delta_{32}) \quad \text{Matter effects}$$

+CP even terms ...

$$\Delta_j = \frac{\Delta m_j^2 L}{4E}$$

$$a = 2\sqrt{2}G_F n_e E$$

Leading term

- Almost full degeneracy between θ_{13} and θ_{23}
- But if θ_{13} is known, ability to resolve the θ_{23} octant!

CP-odd term

- Sensitive to Jarlskog invariant $J_{\text{CP}} = s_{13} c_{13}^2 s_{12} c_{12} s_{23} c_{23} \sin \delta_{\text{CP}}$
- Opposite effect for ν and $\bar{\nu}$

Matter effects

- Sensitive to the sign of Δm_{31}^2 , i.e. mass hierarchy!
- Opposite effect for ν and $\bar{\nu}$

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu) \simeq 1 - \sin^2 2\theta_{\text{eff}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{\text{eff}}^2 L}{4E} \right)$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{\text{eff}} = 4c_{13}^2 s_{23}^2 (1 - c_{13}^2 s_{23}^2)$$

- Poor sensitivity to θ_{13} (only the cos appears)
- Good sensitivity to θ_{23} , **up to the octant!!** (two solutions for s_{23})

$$\Delta m_{\text{eff}}^2 = \Delta m_{31}^2 - (c_{12}^2 - 2 \cos \delta_{\text{CP}} s_{13} t_{23} s_{12} c_{12} \Delta m_{21}^2)$$

- Good sensitivity to $|\Delta m_{\text{atm}}^2| (= |\Delta m_{32}^2| [\text{NO}] / |\Delta m_{31}^2| [\text{IO}])$
- **Mass hierarchy bias** coming from changing sign of Δm_{31}^2 !

Three Unanswered Questions in Neutrino Oscillations

Known: θ_{12} , θ_{13} , Δm_{21}^2 , size of Δm_{32}^2 , $\sin^2(2\theta_{23}) \rightarrow 1$

Three remaining questions for neutrino oscillations:

I. Is there CP violation in the lepton sector?

- Is $\delta_{CP}=0$ (CP conservation), or not?

II. What is the mixing between ν_μ and ν_τ ?

- Is θ_{23} equal 45 (maximal mixing), smaller (lower octant) or larger (upper octant)?

III. What is the mass hierarchy (sing of Δm_{32}^2)?

J-PARC Accelerator (MR) upgrade status

- Stable continuous **~800kW** (FX) operation for users is established!
- : MR power is being improved almost as planned.

JFY2024 - JFY2028 Plans

- RF system upgrade (continued)
- More magnet power supplies for beam correction
- Reinforcement of the main magnet PSs
- Upgrade MR-Abort-Dump

By courtesy of Y. Sato (J-PARC Accelerator)

T2K Near Detectors

Detect unoscillated neutrinos and study their interactions

- All enclosed in a 0.2 T magnet
 - Dedicated π^0 detector (main background for ν_e appearance at the far detector)
 - Time Projection Chambers (TPCs) for 3D tracking, PID, momentum
 - Fine Grained Detectors (CH / H₂O) for tracking
- Significantly reduced systematic uncertainties at the far detector ($\sim 17\% \rightarrow \sim 3\%$)

*Before upgrade

Upgrade of T2K near detector

The near detector was upgraded between 2022 – 2024

- Ongoing calibration and performance studies

Issues of previous near detector:

- limited angular acceptance (Super-K is 360°)
- high proton reconstruction threshold (400 MeV, but our protons start around 200 MeV)

Upgrades:

- POD (π^0) replaced with
 - SuperFGD (2 million plastic scintillator cubes)
 - 2 high-angle TPCs
 - Time of flight detector

Effect of T2K Near Detectors

Detect unoscillated neutrinos and study their interactions

Significantly reduced flux and neutrino interaction systematic uncertainties at the far detector

ν -mode μ -like events at Super-K

ν -mode e-like events at Super-K

New intermediate detector

Fully equipped with multi-PMTs = 19 x 3" PMTs assembles into a "big" PMT

- Far detector will also use 800 mPMTs

Benefits of mPMTs

- Superior photon counting
- Improved angular acceptance
- Extension of dynamic range
- Intrinsic directional sensitivity
- Local coincidences

Results in better vertex and angular resolution

Improvement strongest near detector edges

Photo from WCTE in CERN

Updated PMTs

Fully equipped with multi-PMTs

- ▶ 2X the detection efficiency
- ▶ 1.5x the quantum efficiency
- ▶ Half the timing resolution
- ▶ Box&Line instead of Venetian blind dynode system

PMT production

- ❖ Production of the 50cm PMTs has started on time

Visual inspection & Testing signal for all the PMT is on-going

PMTs for the Inner Detector		
	Super-K	Hyper-K
Number of PMTs	11,129 50cm PMTs	20,000 50cm PMTs (JPN) (+ additional PDs (Oversea))
Photo-sensitive Coverage	40 %	20 %
Single photon efficiency /PMT	~12%	~24%
Dark Rate /PMT	~4 kHz (Typical)	4 kHz (Average)
Timing resolution of 1 photon	~3 nsec	~1.5 nsec

R&D for the 50cm PMT covers is in progress (material test, fabrication method, full validation under water pressure etc.)

Hyper-K sensitivity

Physics category	Parameters	Sensitivity
LBL (1.3MW×10years)	δ precision	7° - 20°
	CPV coverage ($3/5\sigma$)	76%/58%
	$\sin^2\theta_{23}$ error (for 0.5)	± 0.017
ATM+LBL (10 years)	MO determination	$>3.8\sigma$
	Octant determination (3σ)	$ \theta_{23}-45^\circ > 2^\circ$
Proton Decay (20 years)	τ for $e^-\pi^0$ (3σ)	1×10^{35}
	τ for $\bar{\nu}K$ (3σ)	3×10^{34}
Solar (10 years)	Day/Night (from 0/from KL)	$8\sigma/4\sigma$
	Upturn	$>3\sigma$
Supernova	Burst (10kpc)	54k-90k
	Relic	70v's / 10 years

Sensitivity to supernova neutrinos

4.2 σ observation of diffuse supernova neutrino background (DSNB) within 10 years and 5.7 σ in 20 years

- ▶ Especially above 22 MeV
- ▶ Below 22 MeV difficult spallation background
- ▶ No neutron-tagging with Gd compared to SK-Gd

DSNB ~ 18 events/year

Combining beam and atmospheric oscillations

Flagship Hyper-K results will be from the combined analyses

Mass ordering from atmospheric neutrinos

First combined analysis study ongoing

	$\sin^2\theta_{23}$	Atmospheric ν	Atmospheric + beam ν
Mass ordering	0.40	2.2 σ	3.8 σ
	0.60	4.9 σ	6.2 σ
θ_{23} octant	0.45	2.2 σ	6.2 σ
	0.55	1.6 σ	3.6 σ

Hyper-K neutrino oscillations sensitivity

Beam only sensitivity studies submitted to EPJC: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.15019>

5 σ discovery of δ_{CP} violation in 10 years for ~60% of true δ_{CP} values!

- ▶ Assuming known mass ordering – adding atmospheric events will help constrain mass ordering
- ▶ In <3 years for $\delta_{CP} = -\pi/2$
- ▶ Electron neutrino/antineutrino cross section ratio main systematic for CP violation

Hyper-K neutrino oscillations sensitivity

Uncertainties and challenges

High neutrino rates at the far detector will quickly make Hyper-K systematics dominated

Total systematic uncertainty should be reduced to below 2%

Systematic uncertainties

Assumptions and estimates for systematic uncertainties in the new Hyper-K sensitivity study

T2K 2020	1 ring μ -like		1 ring e-like			
Error source	ν -mode	$\bar{\nu}$ -mode	ν -mode + 0 decay	$\bar{\nu}$ -mode + 0 decay	ν -mode + 1 decay	$\nu/\bar{\nu}$ -mode + 0 decay
ND constrained Flux + Cross section	2.1%	3.4%	3.6 %	4.3 %	4.9%	4.4%
Not ND constrained Cross-section	0.5%	2.6%	3.0 %	3.7 %	2.7%	4.1%
Detector	2.1%	1.9%	3.1 %	3.9 %	13.2%	1.1%
All systematics	3.0%	4.0%	4.7 %	5.9 %s	14.1%	4.6%

Improved	1 ring μ -like		1 ring e-like			
Error source	ν -mode	$\bar{\nu}$ -mode	ν -mode + 0 decay	$\bar{\nu}$ -mode + 0 decay	ν -mode + 1 decay	$\nu/\bar{\nu}$ -mode + 0 decay
ND constrained Flux + Cross section	0.9%	0.9 %	1.8 %	1.6%	1.8%	1.9%
Not ND constrained Cross-section	0.4%	0.4 %	1.6 %	1.4%	1.6%	1.9%
Detector	0.8%	0.7 %	1.1 %	1.5%	4.9%	0.4%
All systematics	1.2%	1.1 %	2.1 %	2.2%	5.2%	2.0%

Systematic requirements

IWCD is crucial to control many important systematic uncertainties

Systematic Source	Required Precision	For Which Measurement	Detector	Achievable Precision
$\sigma(\nu_e)/\sigma(\nu_\mu)$	3-5%	CP Violation, δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$, θ_{23} precision at $\sin(\theta_{23})\sim 0.5$	IWCD	3.5-5%
$\sigma(\bar{\nu}_e)/\sigma(\bar{\nu}_\mu)$	3-5%	CP Violation, δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$, θ_{23} precision at $\sin(\theta_{23})\sim 0.5$	IWCD	4-7%
Wrong-sign background normalization	9%	CP Violation, δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$	ND280	TBD (expect <9%)
Intrinsic ν_e , $\bar{\nu}_e$ and NC backgrounds	3-4%	CP Violation, δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$	IWCD	2.3% (neutrino)
Normalization of non-QE with $E_\nu > 0.7$ GeV	5%	θ_{23} precision at $\sin(\theta_{23})\neq 0.5$	IWCD	5% (neutrino)
Normalization of non-QE with all energies	5%	δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$ Δm^2_{32} precision	IWCD, ND280*	5% (IWCD neutrino) <4% (N280 neutrino) <7% (ND280 antineutrino)
Beam Direction	0.6 mrad (4 MeV shift)	δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$ Δm^2_{32} precision	INGRID	<0.3 mrad (<2 MeV)
Removal (binding) energy	4 MeV*	δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$ Δm^2_{32} precision	IWCD, ND280	2.6 MeV (IWCD on O) ~1 MeV (ND280 on C)**
High angle measurement ($\cos\theta < 0.2$)	4%	CP Violation, δ_{CP} precision at $\sin(\delta_{CP})\sim 0$	IWCD, ND280	<4% statistical precision in both detectors
Beam rate monitoring	~1% per day	General monitoring of beam quality	INGRID	<0.5% per day for neutrinos and antineutrinos
Neutron Multiplicity	TBD	Atmospheric neutrino Nucleon decay	IWCD, ND280	<5% IWCD <4% ND280
$\mu\pi^0$ cross section & neutron multiplicity	TBD	$e\pi^0$ proton decay	IWCD	TBD